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Review

A review on factor influencing the involvement of male partner in antenatal care in Nepal

Sharmila Pokharel^{a,b*}

^a Central Department of Education, Tribhuvan University, Kritipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

^b Department of Health Education, Tribhuvan University, Kritipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

*** Corresponding Author**

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Abstract: *Male involvement in antenatal care (ANC) is an operative approach for improving maternal health results. Though women are sole child producers, the participation of men in financial support and other decision making cannot be out looked. This study reviewed different papers from different study area to analyze the involvement of male partner in antenatal care in Nepal. This study used various literatures all over the country. The analysis of the literature review provided some ideas which led in the identification of some important factors like involvement of male in birth preparedness, financial support, birth companionship, decision making for pregnancy and delivery, responsibility for house and children in the absence of female counterparts, etc. As men play an important role in birth preparedness which points towards economic and emotional support, despite the participation of male during birth preparedness is prohibited in some cultures. So, men should be provided with adequate knowledge and information regarding the need of a woman during pregnancy and provide adequate support and involvement during antenatal care. So, this review recommends to take more efforts to provide education to the community to boost the male participation in ANC to improve the women's health and child safety uprooting the prohibitions in cultural background.*

Keywords: *ANC, maternal health, pregnancy, birth preparedness*

1. Introduction

Men are pillars of a family playing a vital role in family decisions, family planning and family advancement, therefore role of male in maternal health care (MHC) is really important to enhance maternal and child health (Craymah et al., 2017). In a male perspective, pregnancy and maternal health issues are women's part of duty. Due to such kind of beliefs most of the male are running out from the responsibility. The practice of male domination also known as patriarchy is highly dominant in developing countries, which unfortunately hinders their participation in maternal health services (Cleland and Ginneken, 1988; Craymah et al., 2017). According to World Health Organization (WHO) it is globally estimated that around 5,00,000 women annually died due to pregnancy related disorders and child birth and

almost 99% of these kind of deaths highly occur in developing countries (Tura, 2011), among which Nepal is also in the list (Bhatta, 2013).

Fig.1. Antenatal care by region around the world; excluding China (Abou-Zahr et al., 2003)

Prenatal care also known as antenatal care (ANC) is an important aspect for every woman during pregnancy. It mostly involves the follow up with the doctor regarding regular medical checkup and nursing care during their sensitive times to prevent any kind of complexities during their delivery, which ultimately promote healthy lifestyle and quality of life of the pregnant women (Gathuto, 2014). Basically the antenatal examination for the pregnant women consists of visits during the first two trimesters i.e. 1st week- 28th week, periodical visits from 28th week- 36th week, weekly visit after 36th week till delivery providing various health facilities which can determine the status of pregnancy to normal, risk and high risk, like physical examinations consisting of medical history collection of the visitor, inspection of body mass index which measures their blood pressure, height and weight. Further investigation involves pelvic examination, Doppler fetal heart rate monitoring and also includes urine and blood tests and also provides a platform where women can discuss their problem with caretaker (Ebba, 2010; Gathuto, 2014; Ongeso and Okoth, 2018).

The specific objective of providing antenatal services is to promote the wellbeing of pregnant women and neonates through the subsequent undertakings (GON, 2011):

- a) Antenatal visit for four times;
- b) Blood Pressure, weight and Fetal Heart Rate monitoring;
- c) Providing Information, Education and Communication (IEC) and behavior Change Communication (BCC) for risks and care during gestation, birth and post-delivery and instant neonatal care for mother and newborn baby and time to time consulting to the suitable health care;
- d) Delivery by skilled birth attendants, blood, transportation and money (Birth preparedness and complication readiness (BPCR) for both normal and obstetric emergencies);
- e) Recognition and supervision of obstacles;

- f) Facility of tetanus toxoid (TT) immunization, iron Tablets, anti-helminthic (Albendazole) to all gestating women and malaria prophylaxis whenever required.

Women's ability to seek health care is rejuvenated by men, but unfortunately, the male counterparts are unfamiliar about women's reproductive health needs or their own. When male and female are aware of each other's health needs, eventually, the understanding and bonding between each other is more bounded which leads them to receive required health services.

In Uganda, some women hired husbands to visit ANC care since their husbands didn't have time to visit the care center with the wives. Simultaneously, it resulted into the following situations (Kariuki and Seruwagi, 2016):

- a) Since, women were unable to convince their counterparts to accompany them during ANC, they hired men who act like their husbands in the health center.
- b) Hiring is ok but they had to pay additional cost during the process is not so easy.
- c) Since, the hired male were not the legitimate partners, the HIV tests conducted at ANC were not valid.
- d) Unfortunately, a woman is at high risk of domestic violence, if her husband finds out that she went with another to health center during ANC visit.

Male participation in ANC

The proliferation in male involvement in parental health services necessitates the suppliers to expand in-depth understanding and awareness of the men's health perceptions, performance and practices. During pregnancy a woman is physically, mentally and emotionally challenged which requires adequate facilities and care, wellbeing and happiness before (antenatal), during (natal) and after delivery (post-natal) (Kariuki and Seruwagi, 2016). Since, pregnancy is a natural phenomenon in conceiving a baby; it generates a lot of emotional demands and physical inconvenience for the mother. Necessary emotional, mental and physical support from husband and his family could result in soothing the status of women's health making family members aware about the women's demand during pregnancy (Chris, 2015). There are several factors influencing the men and women's involvement in MHC:

a) Demographic characteristics

The involvement of male in MHC would increase if the couples are planning for the first child and gradually decrease with the order of the birth. In case a woman previously had still birth, the use of maternal services would increase, since they are already known about the complications during delivery. Women's age is also a determinant factor which is an essential analyst for the use of antenatal care services (Navaneetham and Dharmalingam, 2002).

b) Socio-economic characteristics

The awareness of complications during pregnancy is much higher in women who are educated and involved in jobs. So, job holders and educated women rather than uneducated and unemployed women are eagerly using the maternal health services and are mostly aware about the antenatal care (ANC) services. These days, social media like television, radio, facebook, etc. play an important role in exposing the important information as mass communication media. So, women who are able to utilize such media are also aware about the ideas of maternal health care services.

Rural and urban areas also have a distinct differences due to remoteness in the villages and high availability of health services in the cities. The caste of the people and their religious

beliefs also affect the trend of using maternal health services which might hinder the health seeking behavior of some women (Navaneetham and Dharmalingam, 2002)

The male counterpart is regularly the principal decision maker in a family where the economy of wife also directly depends on her husbands, so majority of decision in a family is carried out by husbands where about half of the wife’s health decision in developing country like Nepal is taken by the males or husbands (NDHS, 2001). In a patriarchal society, decision maker is always man (Bhatta, 2013). Participation of male in optimization of antenatal health services is an important aspect in female’s health (Ongeso and Okoth, 2018). The role of the partners in maternal and child health is mostly neglected since the male counterparts are busy earning money and sustaining the family (Nayana, 2015). Men can enhance gestation and childbearing through retorting to obstacles, pursuing medical assistance, paying for transportation, and distributing domestic capitals (Lewis et al., 2015). Lack of participation of males in maternal health care services creates a loophole in formulating policies and remains a problem for health service providers (Kiptoo and Kipmerewo, 2017). There should be a provision for addressing male involvement in health education since it plays a great role in both maternal and child health outcomes. The expectant fathers should be provided with rules and regulation to strictly visit ANC with their female counterparts during pregnancy and assist them during any complications. Hence this study is a review of factors influencing the involvement of husbands during antenatal care of their partner.

Conceptual framework

Fig.2.Demonstrating the conceptual framework (Ghimire & Pun, 2017)

In order to determine the status of male participation in the antenatal care services the conceptual framework (figure 2) represents various variables. Education, occupation, family beliefs, number of children, type of family and various other factors determine the mentality of a man, due to which he tends to develop his own personal feelings and gratitude towards his responsibilities.

Male involvement in antenatal care in Nepal

Nepal is a developing country with 281 deaths per 100,000 live births indicating high maternal mortality rate in Asia. Several risk factors have been acknowledged which included the lack of skilled care during delivery, hindered health-seeking and deprivation of access to health facilities. Since, 90% of Nepal’s population resides in rural areas, maximal birth occurs at home due to which these cases of delivery are in a huge risk. Only one third of the

deliveries in the rural areas are possible in the health post or hospitals (Amin et al., 2010; CARE USA, 2012; Kearns et al., 2014; Lewis et al., 2015; Punam and Bhawana, 2017). Skilled birth attendants (SBAs) provides services which include antenatal care (ANC) also including delivery and postnatal care. These services are very important for decreasing the maternal and newborn death since they offer on time delivery of pregnant and are able to provide adequate care to the newborn in case of life threatening risks (Joshi et al., 2014). Similarly, a study conducted by Choulagai et al (2013) suggested that only half of the women in their study sites were able to use the delivery services by skilled birth attendance indicating lack of such facilities in rural areas in Nepal. In Nepal childbirth and pregnancy in women are an important health issue. Since, every woman after marriage sacrifice their life for their in-laws, every decision after marriage regarding maternal health, child care and other reproductive rights is carried out by her husband's family. Women during labor and delivery are assisted with same gender helper which actually proliferated issues of poor nutrition, lack of attentiveness, and health seeking practices primarily through the eye of females (Lewis et al., 2015). Recently, the Government of Nepal has aimed to increase the women's participation in attending ANC facilities to 80% (Simkhada et al., 2010).

Table 1. Maternal and child health indicators in Nepal (Kearns et al., 2014)

Indicators	Nepal
Total fertility rate (live births per woman)	2.39
Maternal mortality ratio (per 100,000 live births)	220
Under-five mortality rate (per 1,000 live births)	50
Infant mortality rate (per 1,000 live births)	41
Neonatal mortality rate (per 1,000 live births)	33
Immunization coverage, all basic, among 1-year-olds (%)	87.0
Contraception prevalence rate (% of married women 15–49)	49.7
Unmet need for family planning (%)	27.0
Age at first birth (median, women 25–49)	20.2
Antenatal care coverage, at least 1 visit / 4 visits (%)	58.3/50.1
Births attended by skilled provider (%)	36.0
Births in a health facility (%)	35.3
Birth weight <2500g (%)	12.4
Births by caesarean section (%)	4.6
Postnatal care visit within 2 days of birth (%)	30.1

There are several factors influencing the participation of husbands in antenatal services. One of the important demographic factors mostly includes age. According to Bhatta (2013), a cross-sectional study conducted in 2178 married males between May- December 2010 revealed that age group less than 25 participated less than older aged and mid-aged people. The older people mostly accompanied their partners during antenatal period, birth preparedness, pregnancy and immunization of the child but unfortunately husbands below 25 years were less likely to do so. Since, male participation in ANC is lacking in Nepal due to hesitation, the husbands handed the responsibility to their mother to care their wives. A qualitative study conducted by Simkhada et al (2010) discussed decision making of antenatal care by mother in law suggested that the allocation of resources and decision making power

of mother in law prohibited daughter in law from receiving antenatal care in Nepal. Since mother in law were uneducated and they didn't themselves had ANC services, due to generation gap they hindered their daughter in law to assess the ANC uptake and used the money elsewhere.

Strategies for raising awareness about emergency obstetric conditions of females in men and preparing them for delivery and ready for any complication. Male involvement will enable them to support their spouses to utilize emergency obstetric services early and the preparation for birth and ready themselves for complications. This would lead to a reduction in all three phases of delay and thereby positively impact birth outcomes (Kiptoo and Kipmerewo, 2017).

Discussion

Structural and non-structural determinant of male involvement

Inequality for genders in decision making and obligation for pregnancy, and various community beliefs and principles regarding use of ANC services reflect lacking of male participation in a society. Simkhada et al(2010) reviewed that husband's education, maternal education, marital status, availability of services, household expenses and income, women's job, exposure to media like radio and television, and other dimensions affects the ANC uptake in most developing countries. Cultural beliefs and ideas about pregnancy also had an influence on ANC use in some countries. Here are some of the determinants of male involvement during ANC:

Availability of husbands

The husbands are busy earning money and stay away from home. The availability of husbands in home is also one of the important determinant in involvement of males in maternal health care and antenatal care. When a women needs ANC, due to absence of their male counterparts they have to assess it by oneself or ask help from mother in law (Lewis et al., 2015; Simkhada et al., 2010).

Gaps in knowledge

The quality of ANC use in rural area is less than in urban areas due to lack of knowledge and information regarding the use of health services. Educated and job holder women could assess the health service easily and their husbands would understand the need than the uneducated couples (Simkhada et al., 2010).

Barriers to institutional births

In some societies in Nepal there is strict provision of not using the health center and skilled birth attendant for the delivery. Due to cultural prohibitions, women are forced to deliver in homes with unhygienic condition which ultimately influence the poor health status of mother and child and might prone to child mortality. In rural areas, lack of health facilities during complications force them to travel long distances in order to assess good health facility. One of the difficult barrier to institutional births is transportation and delivery cost in the hospital, which is very expensive. Another loophole in the institution include the unavailability of staffs or SBAs during delivery risking the life of mother and the child.

Quality of ANC

The quality of ANC includes type of health workers i.e. SBAs, doctors, nurse or mid wives providing services to the delivering woman (Joshi et al., 2014). The ANC delivered at health institutions is a key promote mother and child health. The WHO recommends that a range of interventions be delivered as a part of ANC, many of which effectively reduce morbidity and

mortality. An example for this is malaria prophylaxis and preventing or treating iron deficient or anemic women with adequate doses of iron and folate supplements (Andrew et al., 2014). A study conducted by Joshi et al (2014) from the 2011 Nepal Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) which interviewed 12,674 women aged 15–49 years and 4,121 men aged 15–49 years were asked a set of questions regarding antenatal health care. Among them 4079 women included in the analysis, concluded that only half of the women visited four or more ANC visits while other half visited less than four times, which included 15% women who didn't have ANC visit once in their pregnancy. Uneducated husbands and involving in agriculture didn't let their wives visit ANC due to poverty and lack of education.

Table 2: Quality of antenatal care received during last pregnancy for Nepalese women (Joshi et al., 2014)

N= 3520	Total number of Women	%	95% CIs
Given information during pregnancy (Told about pregnancy complications or told where to go for pregnancy complications or advised to use a skilled birth attendant)			
yes	2,872	81.6	78.5-84.4
Iron tablets/syrup taken			
yes	3,214	91.3	89.3-93.0
Given Intestinal Parasite Drugs			
yes	2,250	63.9	60.8-66.9
Two or more tetanus injections given			
yes	3,033	86.2	84.2-87.9
Blood Pressure Measured			
yes	3,043	86.4	83.9-88.6
Blood sample taken			
yes	1,595	45.3	41.8-48.9
Urine sample taken			
yes	1,968	55.9	52.4-59.3
Received seven all ANC components			
	854	24.3	21.6-27.2

Conclusions

Nepal is a developing country still going changes in demography with communities having unequal socio-economic status, castes, ethnicity, religious beliefs and literacy. Since, Nepal is a patriarchal country most of the decision regarding maternal health and child birth is taken by male counterparts supporting the family financially. Despite, the involvement of male in antenatal care and maternal health is poor, they are properly involved in secondary duties which cannot be ignored. Unfortunately due to hindrance in male interference in women's health, the quality of women's health and child health is degrading. Including men in maternal and child health enhancement and educating them regarding possible circumstances and risks during pregnancy can reduce the complications and develop a feeling of responsibility in male counterparts. So, it's very important to educate men regarding women's health and importance of antenatal health services during pregnancy. Hence, from the above literatures, it can be concluded that the male involvement in ANC is merely due to lack of education, unavailability and lack of interest in women's pregnancy.

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